

Successful Aging: A Neuroscientist Explores the Power and Potential of Our Lives

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The standard of individual ageing has been critically redefined by ‘success’ that follows ageing. Although this term or concept of ‘successful ageing’ evolved from a biomedical perspective, it has now become applicable in the realm of social sciences – including management. It must be borne in mind that there is no universally accepted standard definition or description of ‘ageing’; however, basic elements of late-life socio-cultural, mental, environmental and appreciative implications will be included. With this backdrop, Levitin puts forward the multilayered identity for ‘ageing’, through the bases of optimal health. The readership may feel that most of the outcomes are commonsensical, though none of those negates the importance of research-based evidence.

Many misconceptions surrounding the idea of ‘ageing’ have been junked because of this work by Levitin. An individual’s memories, attitudes, social interactions, habits, experiences and professional exposure can influence the respective brain’s growth, supported by adequate coordination between nerves and muscle-driven activities. Levitin posits that it’s imperative to improve the possibilities of remaining alert, joyful, focused, intelligent and professional even while growing older – these are probable via his generic suggestions.

Labelling ‘ageing’ as ‘failure’ or a phase of ‘decay’ is not advisable. It will rather be wiser, according to the author, to think of ‘ageing’ as a unique developmental stage which may or may not be demanding and has a set of advantages (including disadvantages). The core philosophy behind successful ageing is strong mental and relational performance during the later years of one’s proficient engagement, which can very well maximize the number of balanced (in terms of work and life) and active (in terms of regular contributions towards various organizations/institutions) years of one’s otherwise mundane or stereotype existence.

It will be interesting to note that environmental factors can positively or negatively impact how the perception of ‘ageing’ is shaped in different individuals. Levitin asserts that a community’s interactions with the outside world, based on the established habits of its members, can modify the notional tendencies of ‘ageing’.

The book has demonstrated how an individual’s attitudes, beliefs and value systems may impress upon characteristic ‘ageing’, which also meant that the level of core competencies can justify the significance of ‘ageing’ as contained in society. In Chapter 4, the COACH (Curiosity, Openness,

Associations, Conscientiousness, and Healthy practices) has been described, which will ensure fruitfulness as far as ‘ageing’ is concerned.

Amidst a myriad of things, flexibility would entail necessary willingness to conduct relevant experiments to gauge whether enthusiasm for fresh concepts exists within individual selves and whether off-beat methods of performing tasks are appreciated enough. With augmented maturity, the natural inclination towards rejecting fresh but radical concepts and adhering to the tried and tested path of the past instead may give rise to potential intellectual loss. Therefore, ‘ageing’ must not be allowed to control or initiate professional degradation of individuals.

In the latter phase of the book, Levitin states that we are supposed to remain utterly conscious of our involuntary and voluntary actions. It will help in combating arrogance to achieve the same desired outcomes repeatedly. It is also critical to connect with absolute strangers, especially the younger generations, and go ahead with trying unsullied conceptions and theories in order to let innovation proliferate within organizational set-ups. Highly risky activities may still be discarded; however, a novel deliberation should be considered for sure!

“Successful Aging: A Neuroscientist explores the power and potential of our lives” outlined an exceedingly effective scheme to achieve ‘successful ageing’. Pocnet et al. (2021) believe that older and experienced individuals have already gathered more knowledge and insights by virtue of their longevity. Scholars, researchers, other experts from the field of Knowledge Management opine that this results in an expanded capacity for general trend extraction, recognizing unique patterns, spotting convergence of views and understanding of connections between contexts or environments can lead to improvised comprehending skills and problem-solving acumen. This book is strongly recommended because it serves as a near-to-perfect reminder to people that being meticulous, being amenable to opportunities, maintaining winning relationships with almost everyone possible, being fervent and passionate, and sticking to a healthier lifestyle, which involves nutritious food, decent sleep, and exercise are always decisive from the viewpoint of continued workplace excellence.

Reference:

Pocnet, C., Popp, J., and Jopp, D. (2020). The power of personality in successful ageing: a comprehensive review of larger quantitative studies. *Euro. J. Ageing*. DOI: 10.1007/s10433-020-00

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